

International Dual-Degree Programs: Learning Experience in Student's Perspective

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Abstract

International dual-degree programs have been attractive and well accepted by students and parents, as earning an additional degree from another country is perceived as having better job opportunities. The program developers have tried their best to collaborate to put together attractive and useful content for the programs to meet the expectation. However, what the students experience is far beyond fulfill the program credits at both universities to graduate. They encounter and may have to adjust themselves back and forth for different styles of teaching, different learning environment, and unavoidable cultural difference. Presented in this paper are the viewpoints of the students who have graduated from an International dual- master's degree program in Industrial Engineering. The students' perspective on their two-year dual degree learning journey is described based on the two different educational environments and the process of self-recognition experiences.

Keywords: International dual-degree programs, dual- master's degree program, master of industrial engineering, learning experience

1 Introduction

In recent years, the issue of internationalization is getting more and more attention from people. Many students have planned to broaden their international horizons by studying abroad. A lot of universities have cooperated with overseas schools to establish a dual degree or triple degree courses. The key motivations for launching dual degree programs appear to revolve largely around advancing the internationalization of the campus and raising the institution's international visibility and prestige (Kuder & Obst, 2009). Therefore, the construction of a cooperative relationship through dual degree programs can be strategic with a long-term vision, which is not only beneficial to students and participating institutions, but also local economic development and social prosperity.

Taking the example of Taiwan, the latest data shows that the number of Taiwanese students studying in the dual degree system in the 2018 school year has reached 1541, which is an increase of more than 40% compared with 1092 in the previous year. Taiwan's Ministry of Education's "Public School Information Open Platform" statistics show that in 2018, the number of dual-education partnerships between Taiwanese colleges and universities and overseas schools reached 3583, which is an increase of more than 500 compared with 3080 in 2017. There are also more and more students intending to study abroad for multinational degrees, which is one of the important indicators of university internationalization. Therefore, we can learn that to cope with the impact of the globalization of the higher education market and enhance competitiveness, the dual degree program is one of the international academic exchange strategies.

This paper discusses the viewpoints of the students who have graduated from an International dual- master's degree program in Industrial Engineering between Tunghai University and the Asian Institute of Technology. Forth for different styles of teaching, different learning environment, and unavoidable cultural difference. The students' perspective on their two-year dual degree learning journey is described based on the two different educational environments and the process of self-recognition experiences.

1.1 Tunghai University

Tunghai University is the first comprehensive university with a Christian background in Taiwan. As a student majoring in industrial engineering, the Department of Industrial Engineering and Enterprise Information at

Tunghai University has been cultivating educational cooperation and exchanges with overseas partner universities for many years. In particular, the department and its partner universities Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) signed a dual degree program of master's degree in 2016. According to the contract, after completing the required credits for graduation from the two schools and completing the thesis, students could obtain two master's degrees from Tunghai University and AIT.

1.2 Asian Institute of Technology

Asian Institute of Technology is an international institute of higher learning located in Bangkok, Thailand. It is Asia's pioneer institution established in 1959 to help meet the region's growing needs for advanced learning in engineering, science, technology and management, research and capacity building. AIT's mission is to develop highly qualified and committed professionals who will play a leading role in the sustainable development of the region and its integration into the global economy. A medium of instruction is English.

2 Dual degree program

2.1 Comparisons of current way of overseas study

At present, there are three most common ways to study abroad, which are a direct application, a dual degree program, or an exchange program. Students, after completion of the program, will receive their degree certificates for the direct application and the dual degree program. For the dual degree program, the students will earn degrees from both the home university and the partner university. Compared with the duration of the other two options which is usually one to two years, the duration of the exchange program is mostly one to two semesters, but the students will not receive a degree from the universities they go for exchange.

The common thing between these three options is that most foreign schools are full English-spoken courses, and students must have an English proficiency test certificate when applying. For study fees, students enrolling in the direct program or exchange program only need to pay the tuition of their home school, but for the dual degree program, the students need to pay both tuition fees. Since exchange students do not have graduation thesis requirements, it is conceivable that the pressure is much lower than the other two. By consolidating the above-mentioned information is shown in Table 1. By allowing the students to obtain two degrees at the same time makes the program attractive and it is the reason why more and more people have chosen this way as studying aboard in recent years.

Table 1. Comparisons of current way of overseas study

	Exchange Program	Dual Degree	Independent application
Degree	X	O	O
Courses	High degree of freedom	*	*
Time limitation	1~2 semester	1~2 year	1~2 year
Number of applicants	Many (Competition with students from the same school)	Many (Competition with students from the same school)	Many (Competition with students from multiple countries)
Verification in English (2nd language)	O	O	O
Scholarship	Less opportunities	*	*
GRE/GMAT	X	X	*
Interview from the partner universities	X	*	*
Tuition of the partner universities	X	O	O
Thesis requirement	X	O	O
Pressure	Low	High	High
Advantage	1. Cost savings: less expensive than the dual degree. 2. Broaden horizons.	1. Save time: get two degrees at once. 2. Increase self-competitiveness.	1. Focus on one academic system.

* = According to school regulations

2.2 The pros and cons of dual degree programs

Although there are many claimed benefits for the dual degree program, but the initial implementation has faced a wide range of major challenges, ranging from national policies and regulations to institutional differences and extra administrative work at a personal level. Li (2010) concisely presented these points as follows:

- (1) Different education systems/regulations and accreditation requirements.
- (2) Difficulty in coordinating academic requirements, credits, and quality assurance.
- (3) Different tuition and cost structures between participating universities.
- (4) Difficulties related to the legal review, approval process, and administrative supports.
- (5) Heavy workload during preparation and set-up that often produces very few students.

Since the amount of the student who is interested in joining the dual degree program has increased, the problems mentioned by Li (2010) have been solved and keep on improving. The pros and cons in three different aspects of being a student of dual degree program is shown as follows:

- **Broaden one's knowledge and skillsets.** The biggest benefit is that students get to learn more knowledge from different sites or even more than one field of study. On the other hand, students must spend more time researching without a chance to have work experience.
- **Choices in terms of potential career paths.** Studying further gains one's experience and knowledge from both places. Students may have a better selection of relevant jobs after graduating from school. On the other hand, it does not mean there is a guarantee that it would necessarily increase your income potential.
- **Time and Money on a graduate degree.** As a student of a dual master degree program, we saved time on what we would have spent if we pursued both masters separately. On the other hand, students still have to spend a lot of money upfront for things such as tuition and dormitory fees.

2.3 Recent dual degree program

The dual degree of international university cooperation allows Taiwan students to waive the certification requirements of TOEFL, TOEIC, GRE, or other admission tests after at least two semesters of study at the original school, and continue directly to the foreign university with the cooperation agreement to take the remaining credits. As long as the graduation conditions of the two schools are met, the degrees awarded by the two schools can be obtained. At present, in addition to the bachelor, master, and doctor of the same level, there are also a multi-level master's degree and master's doctorate. The length of the study depends on the content of the contract with the partner university. In the contract for the first year of enrollment, the calculation method of the credits of both parties, how to conduct a thesis and graduation oral exam, and the use of language are clearly defined. For the different types of dual degree programs for master degrees, the respective descriptions are presented in tables 2.

Table 2. Recent dual degree programs (Da Xue Wen,2019)

Degree	Program	Description
Bachelor + Master	3+2	Freshmen to juniors attended the original school. Senior year to partner universities. After completing the graduation credits, continue to study for a year of graduate courses.
	3+1+1	Freshmen to juniors attended the original school. Senior started to study the graduate course. After graduating from partner universities, continue to study for a year of postgraduate courses.
	4+1	Freshmen to seniors attend their original school. After graduation, go-to partner universities to take a one-year postgraduate course.
Dual master	1+1	The first year of graduate school was in the original school. The second year of the graduate school goes to the partner universities.
Master + PhD	1+N	The first year of graduate school was in the original school. By the doctoral studies, graduation conditions and contract provisions of the two universities.

Taking our own example, the contract of the dual degree program signed between Tunghai University and AIT is different from the situation described above, and it takes one semester as the cycle unit. In other words, during these two-year master's studies journey, I flighted back and forth between Taiwan and Thailand every six months.

3 Our learning experience with multi-culture

3.1 Education system experience

The education system of AIT follows the US educational system. The first semester is from August to December, and the second semester is from January to May; the education system of Tunghai University is based on Taiwan's education system. The first semester is from September to January, and the second semester is from February to June. Under this dual degree program, there will be a semester overlap half of the time in January. Therefore, we must prepare to complete the final reports and exams of Tunghai University's courses in advance and must acquire information on the courses registered at AIT whether there are any assignments during the overlapping period.

At Tunghai University, students work more individually than in groups. AIT provides students with two-way interaction between teachers and students. Students are asked to think independently and encouraged to raise questions. Besides, although there are fewer compulsory credits in AIT, each course focuses more on group cooperation and brainstorming during classes and group discussion after the class. Therefore, we spent a lot of time on the team working, conceivable that self-learning time was therefore compressed, so the management of time allocation was something we learned.

3.2 School life experience

In terms of class size, there are about twenty students in each class at Tunghai University. Because of the various choices of the course, we do not have the same group of classmates in every course. Also, even if there are still group reports in the course, most of the assignments can be completed independently by the students. So there is less connection between the students. Therefore, we will normally have a party at the end of each semester for teachers and students to get together. We call it "Final Examination Supplementation". Besides, the main student body of Tunghai University is college students. Therefore, even if there are many extracurricular activities organized by the student union, most of the activities are within the college students. There are fewer opportunities for master students to know friends from other departments.

In the course of the international dual degree program, an ability to communicate in English plays an important role, especially when there are many group reports that require a lot of discussions. In addition to acquiring technical knowledge, improving English ability is also one of the goals pursued by students of an international twin degree. For us, we encouraged ourselves to change our minds and tried to express ideas. Our classmates and friends at AIT were also very compassionate and willing to give us help. Also, we actively participated in extracurricular sports activities organized by the Student Union, including basketball games, chair ball games, and pétanque games. Many of these sports were new to us. Take the game of pétanque as an example, the other players were all from the same country and had already been familiar with the game. We were welcomed to join and they patiently taught us the rules. We met new friends and practice our English through sports. We realized that our English has also improved greatly.

Having roommates from other countries also played an important role in our AIT learning journey. We have different cultures and living habits. Diets are also very different. Having meals together allowed us to learn about their foods and cultures. This is a memorable experience.

3.3 Self-retrospect

We would like to use GREAT, which represents grow, revise, earn, accumulate and transform to describe our learning journey. In the study journey, various emotions were also an important part of my growth, we can better understand how we have grown up in this experience every time we face difficulties in the future.

3.3.1 How have we Grown up during the journey of the international dual degree program?

After experiencing as students of international dual degree programs, we start to look at things differently. Through good time and bad time we went through, we have learned not to be rigid to our initial thoughts but to open our minds to accept things as our new experience. We have learned to live beyond a comfort zone. We have learned to overcome the fear of change. These days when we encounter problems, rather than being panic, we begin to analyze the situation and seek available solutions prior to action. The change in our mindset has been the most important growth in this experience.

We are also aware of the importance of self-responsibility. We live alone far from our hometowns. Especially in the face of academic pressure and the frustration of research bottlenecks, self-regulation is a breakthrough in our internal growth. This must be a rare and commendable opportunity to improve ourselves.

3.3.2 What have we Revised ourselves, including study method and mood?

English was a major barrier in our communication with foreigners. We were reluctant to speak in English. We were afraid that they could not understand. Instead of focusing on the contents of our messages, we paid too much attention to the structure of the language. With much more opportunity to use daily, we have been able to express our opinions with confidence. The lack of language ability is no longer the biggest obstacle to the communication process, and learning has become more effective.

In the past, we learned to complete our work independently, but through teaching and learning methods, we have been encouraged to work as a team. Now we learn to manage our time, work in a team, and spare time for individual activities. We have accumulated a lot of experience in many teamwork and also confident to share our opinions. We know how to help each other in groups, play our role well, and become a member of the team that contributes to teamwork.

3.3.3 What do we Earn from the experience of an international dual degree program?

Through the experience of the international dual degree program, the most direct thing we have earned is that we have obtained two master degrees as we planned for. Besides, we have gained many transversal skills in multiple grouping and personal reporting experiences, especially the ability of thinking and learning, also the ability to read, interact and express. Now we can more effectively capture what the literature mainly focused while doing research, and arranged it in an organized way to present to the listener. These abilities can only be earned through real experience and contact with practical problems.

3.3.4 What would the experience Accumulate in our life?

As an international dual degree student, the experience we have is different from studying abroad, but to master the pros and cons of both places at the same time. This is undoubtedly the accumulation of another experience in our life stage. Besides, we also know many friends from various countries. By communicating with classmates and friends from different countries, we have a deeper understanding of things in different cultures. In addition to knowing new knowledge with a broader mind, we have also accumulated many experiences in making friends with different cultural backgrounds. As a result, our international outlook has developed a lot, and accumulating our international competitiveness will definitely help us in our job application in the future.

3.3.5 What do we Transform after study with a dual degree?

With this commendable experience, both of us know ourselves better. The growth and achievements also bring to ourselves after we overcome the problems that have made a big difference in our views and personalities. One of us has changed from a shy personality who was not good at expressing our thought in the past to someone who can confidently express our ideas with others and even give opinions.

In addition, we never had enough courage to easily try unknown things in the past, and now we know clearly that the experience accumulated after trying will be the best way to promote our growth. As a student of the international dual degree program, there must be some hardships during the study journey, but the growth and accomplishment that the experience gives us have made us great progress in all aspects. We would say that this must be one of the most worthwhile experiences for us.

4 Conclusion

Through the international dual degree program, we experienced several new things that required us to make adjustments. Such as the improvement of English ability and changing the mind of accepting new things, etc. Transversal skills make us confident to show our opinions to others and manage a team. In today's society, more and more people emphasize one's international competitiveness, many people seek to have experience of studying abroad or working abroad. The friends we have known from many other countries during this study journey also plays an important part in the way we improve our self-competitiveness. Apart from this, we not only gain professional knowledge, but also experienced a lot of different cultures by visiting some famous local attractions after classes.

Overall, studying for a dual degree program can not only reduce the amount of money spent in the past to study abroad and the time required to study a second degree, but also graduate early and enter the workplace as early as possible. We had gained international learning experience, enhance our international competitiveness, and make ourselves a sought-after talent for multinational companies at the same time. Although there are good times and bad times in this experience, we still believe no matters the internal or external growth we earned would be worthwhile in our life.

5 References

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